

Hepatitis B related Hepatocellular Carcinoma- Acute and Uncommon Presentation

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Abstract

Introduction- Hepatitis B virus (HBV) impacts large number of populations worldwide and has both hepatic and extrahepatic manifestations. It can present as acute hepatitis, chronic hepatitis, cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC). The available data provide evidence that HBV infection is associated with the risk of developing HCC with or without an underlying liver cirrhosis, due to various direct and indirect mechanisms promoting hepatocarcinogenesis.

Case Report- We report a sixty-year-old male, not a known case of any chronic illness presented with distension of abdomen. and jaundice of two weeks duration only. On evaluation he was diagnosed to be having hepatitis B related cirrhosis of liver with multifocal hepatocellular carcinoma. His ultrasonogram showed altered echotexture of liver with suspicious lesions in both lobes of liver with gross ascites. On subjecting to Triple phase Computed tomography scan confirmed ultrasonography findings and suspicious lesions showed multiple lesions in both lobes of liver with enhancement on arterial phase and wash out on venous and portal phase. His liver function tests were deranged; Alpha feto protein level (AFP) was massively raised to 28,253 I.U.and HBV DNA quantitative was four lakh I.U/ml. The upper gastro-intestinal endoscopy revealed low grade esophageal varices. He was married and had four children and on family screening, all were found to be HbsAg negative and were vaccinated against the same.

Conclusion- Hepatitis B has many presentations varying from inactive carrier stage in majority to cirrhosis and H.C.C but presenting for first time with multifocal H.C.C in advanced stage with such short duration of illness is uncommon, thus making treating health professionals for becoming more vigil for such deadly and acute catastrophic face of Hepatitis B.

Keywords- Chronic hepatitis B, Hepatocellular carcinoma, Jaundice, Ascites, Esophageal Varices

INTRODUCTION- HBV infection has become major health problem in developing country like India which has many hotspots like Haryana, Punjab, Uttar Pradesh, Uttarakhand, North eastern states and Hepatitis B Surface Antigen (HbsAg) positivity varies between 2–4.7% [1,2]. In India, approximately 40 million people are chronically infected with Hepatitis B [3]. The major routes of transmission of Hepatitis B include vertical transmission, unsafe needle & sexual practices, repeated exposure to blood & blood products like who receive repeated transfusion of blood, are on maintenance haemodialysis, intravenous drug abusers, males having sex with male, female sex workers, sexual partners & care takers of HBV patient and prisoners [4]. The molecular profile of HBV-HCC is extensively and continuously under study, and it is the result of altered molecular pathways, which modify the microenvironment and lead to DNA damage. HBV produces the protein HBx, which has a central role in the oncogenetic process. Proper management of the underlying HBV-related liver disease is fundamental, including HCC surveillance, viral suppression, and application of adequate predictive models. When HBV-HCC occurs, liver function and HCC characteristics guide the physician among treatment strategies [5].

CASE REPORT - We report a sixty- year-old male, not a known case of any chronic illness presented with distension of abdomen and jaundice for only last two weeks duration. There was no history of fever, weight loss, haematemesis, melena, altered sleep pattern or behaviour, bladder or bowel symptoms, breathlessness on exertion or rest. On biochemical evaluation he had pancytopenia on complete hemogram, liver function test was deranged i.e. there was low albumin level, mild hyperbilirubinemia, raised transaminitis with reversal of ratio of AST being more than ALT and increased INR. The lipid profile showed lower values of all parameters including total cholesterol, triglycerides, LDL, VLDL and HDL levels. His renal function test, serum electrolytes and blood sugar level were in normal range. The viral screen was positive for HbsAg but anti HCV antibody, anti-HIV antibody, Serum IgM HAV & HEV antibody test were negative, Alpha feto protein level (AFP) was significantly raised to 28,253 I.U.and HBV DNA quantitative was four lakhs I.U/ml. His ultrasonogram showed altered echotexture of liver with suspicious lesions in both lobes of liver with gross ascites. Triple phase Computed tomography scan confirmed ultrasonography findings and suspicious lesions showed multiple lesions in both lobes of liver which showed enhancement on arterial phase and wash out on venous and portal phase. He was diagnosed to be having hepatitis B related cirrhosis of liver with multifocal hepatocellular carcinoma. The upper gastro-intestinal endoscopy revealed low grade esophageal varices. He was married and had four children and on family screening, all were found to be HbsAg negative and were vaccinated against the same. Liver transplant surgeon and surgical oncologist were consulted who ruled out liver transplantation or any other intervention, in view of multiple lesions in both lobes of liver with cirrhotic background. He was started on diuretics, rotatory oral antibiotics, multivitamins, calcium & vitamin D3 supplementation, lactulose, high vegetable protein and fluid restricted diet. He came for consultation for next one month but then was lost to follow up.

Figure 1- Triple Phase CT Scan abdomen Showing enhancing lesions in both lobes of liver in arterial phase

Figure 2- Triple Phase CT Scan abdomen Showing washout of lesions in Portal phase

Figure 3- Triple phase CT scan Showing complete washout of lesions in venous phase

DISCUSSION- The World Health Organization (WHO) aims at reducing HBV infections by 90% and increasing global vaccine coverage to 90% [6] for which health awareness is mandatory regarding hepatitis B prevention, screening, and vaccination [7]. The HBV infection behaves like tip of iceberg where 90% of patients are unaware about it, thus remain undiagnosed and in future can progress to cirrhosis, and HCC [8]. Liver cancer is important cause of mortality associated with cancer pan globally with annual death toll of 700,000 [9]. Hepatocellular Carcinoma (HCC) represent the major variety of primary liver malignancies and is responsible for 70% to 85% of the total liver cancer burden [10]. The maximum cases of hepatocellular carcinoma (75% to 90%) develop in cirrhotic liver caused by various factors like chronic HBV & HCV, alcohol, obesity and diabetes mellitus, autoimmune hepatitis or hemochromatosis [11-13]. In last three decades, about 63% increase in total deaths has been reported globally because of viral hepatitis HBV & HCV infections because it leads to continuous liver damage which gradually progresses to cirrhosis and H.C.C [14]. HCC has occurred even at two years of age in areas with high prevalent rate and its incidence increases with age in all populations. HCC has a male predominance. The greater exposure of HBV & HCV infection and aflatoxin in African and Asian countries is an important reason for detection of 80% of all HCC cases from these areas [15-17]. The areas with less screening & vaccination and limited availability of treatment are detrimental in control of HBV infection [18]. The incidence of HCC in chronic HBV & HCV infection is 44%, and 21% respectively. In our case, uncommon thing was its first presentation with abdominal distension and jaundice of very short duration and on evaluation, multifocal H.C.C in both lobes of liver was detected which rendered the patient out of any option of liver transplantation, surgical

intervention or Trans arterial chemoembolization (TACE) in view of decompensation. Other uncommon presentation of HBV related H.C.C in very young age with short duration history and with rupture have been reported in literature [18,19].

CONCLUSION- Hepatitis B has many presentations varying from inactive carrier stage to chronic hepatitis, followed by cirrhosis and H.C.C in significant percentage of patients but presenting for first time with multifocal H.C.C in such a small duration of clinical symptoms is not common, thus making treating health professionals for becoming more vigil for such deadly and acute catastrophic face of Hepatitis B.

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